

Software Title:

"Detector of Manipulations and Subtexts"

Program Description:

Summary:

The software is designed for automatic analysis of textual data to detect manipulative techniques, hidden subtexts, and metaphors in online content. It can be applied in journalism, analytics, marketing, education, and combating disinformation.

Key Features:

- 1. Detection of Manipulative Techniques:**
 - Identifies rhetorical techniques aimed at distorting perception:
 - Appeal to fear (e.g., "*the country will lose its independence*").
 - False generalizations (e.g., "*they always make decisions for us*").
 - Misrepresentation or manipulation of facts.
 - 2. Detection of Hidden Subtexts:**
 - Automatic identification of:
 - Irony and sarcasm.
 - Implied meanings not explicitly expressed.
 - 3. Metaphor Recognition and Interpretation:**
 - Detects metaphors and identifies their role in shaping text perception (e.g., "*swamp*" → negative framing).
 - 4. Data Visualization:**
 - Highlights key manipulative phrases and metaphors in the text.
 - Builds semantic and framing maps to visually demonstrate manipulations.
 - 5. Dynamic Analysis:**
 - Compares texts from different sources to detect shifts in subtexts and manipulative techniques.
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Applications:

- **Journalism:** Automatic analysis of bias and manipulations in news articles.
 - **Business and Marketing:** Adaptation of advertising texts for different cultural contexts while avoiding unethical manipulations.
 - **Education:** Teaching critical thinking through the identification of subtexts and manipulations.
 - **Social Media:** Detection of disinformation and manipulative messaging.
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Technical Specifications:

- 1. Linguistic Foundation:**

- Uses NLP (Natural Language Processing) techniques for natural language analysis.
 - Integration of pre-trained machine learning models (e.g., BERT or GPT).
 - 2. **Architecture:**
 - **Frontend:** Browser extension (JavaScript).
 - **Backend:** Python server (Flask/FastAPI) interacting with NLP models.
 - **Data Storage and Processing:** SQL/NoSQL databases.
 - 3. **Input/Output Format:**
 - **Input:** Text fragments extracted from web pages.
 - **Output:**
 - Highlighted manipulative phrases with explanations.
 - Visual representation of frames and subtexts.
 - 4. **Programming Languages:**
 - Python, JavaScript (HTML/CSS), NLP libraries (spaCy, Hugging Face), D3.js for visualization.
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Uniqueness of the Software:

1. Integration of **manipulation detection, subtext analysis, and metaphor recognition** in a single tool.
 2. Visual representation of semantic frames and shifts in meanings for clear analysis.
 3. Real-time application for analyzing texts in browsers.
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Authorship:

Developer of the idea and logic: **Arina (Aleksandrovna) Karaseva**

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